

Acknowledgement

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The Kinetic Analysis of Consecutive Irreversible First Order Reaction. Oxidation of Benzhydrazide by Peroxydisulphate

M. B. HOGALE*, M. H. JAGDALE and B. P. NIKAM
Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University,
Kolhapur-416 004

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STUDIES on consecutive reactions, including the oxidation by peroxydisulphate¹ are rather limited. Jagdale and Kadam² investigated the silver(I) catalysed oxidation of succinimide by peroxydisulphate and interpreted the results in terms of consecutive reactions. This communication reports the oxidation of benzhydrazide by peroxydisulphate along with a proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate (A.R.), benzhydrazide (B.D.H.), silver nitrate (AnalaR) and other chemicals used were of either E. Merck or B.D.H.

All the solutions were prepared in distilled water. The reaction was carried out in thermostated water-bath at 35° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) for 240 min. The kinetics were followed by estimating the remaining peroxydisulphate by the method of Szabo *et al.*³ further modified by Khulbe and Srivastva⁴.

Results

The concentrations of benzhydrazide, benzoyldiimide and nitrogen (A, B and C, respectively) formed at any time t can be calculated readily by applying the method of Esson⁵. A series of first order reactions can be fitted by plotting concentrations of A, B, C against time (Fig. 1) from the curve of concentration of A against time; k_1 , the rate constant for oxidation of benzhydrazide into benzoyldiimide was found to be $1.91 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The equations for concentrations of A, B and C can be put in simple form by introducing dimensionless parameters⁶ such as α , β , γ , τ and K . Thus α , β and γ were essentially concentrations relative to the initial value A_0 and can vary in the range 0-1 as shown in Table 1. The concentrations of intermediate B as measured by β passes through a

Fig. 1. Plot of concentration of A, B and C against time: (A) benzhydrazide, (B) benzoyldiimide, and (C) nitrogen.

maximum value which depends on K , the relative value of the rate constant. The maximum value of τ is 2.23, β (max) = 0.72 and B (max) = 7.01 ml for benzoyldiimide. The induction period for benzoyldiimide is 200 min.

Swain's time-ratio method⁷ has been used for accurate determination of the rate constants for

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AND DIMENSIONLESS PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF BENZHYDRAZIDE BY PEROXYDISULPHATE

Temp. = 35°

 $k = 2.20 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ rate constant for overall oxidation, $k_1 = 1.91 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for oxidation of benzhydrazide and $k_2 = 2.87 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for oxidation of benzoyldiimide

Time min	$\tau = k_1 t$	$\alpha = \frac{A}{A_0}$	$\beta = \frac{B}{A_0}$	$\gamma = \frac{C}{A_0}$	$(1 - \alpha)$	$\delta = \beta + 2\gamma$	50 δ	$K = k_2/k_1$ (mean)
00	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
10	0.12	0.94	0.12	0.001	0.06	0.12	6.0	—
20	0.23	0.89	0.20	0.004	0.11	0.21	10.5	—
30	0.34	0.84	0.28	0.008	0.16	0.30	15.0	—
40	0.46	0.79	0.35	0.013	0.21	0.38	19.0	—
50	0.57	0.74	0.42	0.02	0.26	0.46	23.0	—
60	0.69	0.69	0.47	0.03	0.31	0.53	26.5	—
80	0.92	0.64	0.56	0.05	0.36	0.66	33.0	0.15
100	1.15	0.58	0.62	0.07	0.42	0.76	38.0	—
120	1.38	0.53	0.66	0.09	0.47	0.84	42.0	—
150	1.72	0.45	0.70	0.12	0.55	0.94	47.0	—
180	2.06	0.38	0.71	0.16	0.62	1.03	51.5	—
210	2.41	0.32	0.71	0.23	0.68	1.17	58.5	—
240	2.75	0.28	0.70	0.23	0.72	1.16	58.0	—

[S₂O₈²⁻] = 0.01 M, [Ag⁺] = 1 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Benzhydrazide] = 0.1 M.

competing first order reactions (Table 1). The graphs⁶ of K vs τ were plotted for certain $\delta = 0.30, 0.70$ and 1.40 for 15, 35 and 70 percent reactions, respectively. The mean value obtained for a relative rate constant K was found to be 0.15 from the corresponding value of τ , k_1 was calculated ($\tau = k_1 t$), while k_2 , evaluated by using the equation $K = k_2/k_1$, was found to be equal to $2.87 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Thus, the sum of values of k_1 and k_2 calculated by Swain's method was found to be equal to k , the rate constant for overall reaction.

Mechanism of reaction: According to Haskar and Mehrotra⁸, the hydrazides undergo first hydride abstraction by electron seeking species to form diimide intermediate. In the present reaction, benzhydrazide is initially oxidised to benzoyldiimide *in situ* which is further converted into benzoic acid and nitrogen. This was further supported by the observation of Kelly *et al.*⁹ for the phenyl acetyl hydrazide oxidation by Mn^{II}. The following scheme for the oxidation of benzhydrazide has been proposed.

First two steps have been proposed by Bawn and Margerson¹⁰ and Srivastava and Singh¹¹. The reaction was studied under pseudo-first order condition, *i.e.* [substrate] $\gg$ [S₂O₈²⁻]. Thus, the order with respect to substrate is zero. Here, k_1 and k_2 , the rate constants for the first and second step of the reaction calculated by Swain's time-ratio

method, indicate that the conversion of benzhydrazide into benzoyldiimide is fast as compared with the conversion of diimide into benzoic acid and nitrogen. The general reaction scheme proposed for other substrates^{1,2} can be applied to benzhydrazide oxidation by peroxydisulphate.

The experimental results obtained provide evidence in support of consecutive reaction.

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